

TANGASAN: THE TRADITIONAL RITUAL OF BARANGAY BUKID PARANG SULU PHILIPPINES

Faranaz M. Jimlan, Maryjoy A. Busaña-Ibno, Marsiyada R. Saripul, Mailyln S. Taji, Muniezha S. Malik, Nashreena J. Bariwa, Junalyn A. Mawali, Alnie J. Bada, Al-Rahden T. Ganih, Marlon T. Turang, Almoder A. Jairah

Mindanao State University-Sulu, Capitol Site, Jolo Sulu, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the significance of the traditional ritual, Tangasan. The researcher aims to explore the history of this tradition, which represents cultural transmission and highlights the value of this ritual in the society of Barangay Bukid, Parang-Sulu. The purpose of this study is to gain a deeper understanding of the history and significance of this tradition. The researchers aim to share the knowledge gained from the participants with the people, particularly the younger generation, to emphasize the importance of cultural heritage, encourage them to value, and respect their own traditions. This study employed a case study-ethnography approach to examine the significance of this tradition. The researchers used qualitative thematic analysis, coding responses from interviews into themes. Face-to-face interviews and documentation were the primary instruments. Moreover, the results of this study reveal the significant value of the Tangasan tradition, which is unique to Barangay Bukid, Parang-Sulu. This tradition has become a practice for generations, passing down its significance through the years. This study provides valuable knowledge and insights, highlighting the importance of preserving cultural heritage. The researchers discovered numerous lessons that can be treasured in various ways, and the history behind this tradition is unique and highly respected by the residents of Bukid.

Keywords: *traditional ritual, significant value, gaining knowledge, sharing knowledge, generations*

INTRODUCTION

Traditional ritual primary focus on specific practices, ceremonies or customs performed by community or society. Tangasan holds significant value for the community of Barangay Bukid, particularly for the creators of this tradition. The researchers aim to investigate this tradition to understand its value and preserve cultural heritage.

Tangasan, the traditional ritual of barangay Bukid Parang-Sulu provides knowledge, and acknowledges the new generation to know the importance of traditional culture in society. The word "tangas" (or "taas") means "too high," which is why they called it "Tangasan" due to its association with the mountain. The tradition, Tangasan was established many years ago, originating from the datu in their community and the person who founded this tradition. The process of this tradition requires every participant to make 44 kinds of Tausug delicacies (bang-bang sug) with three chickens, each of specific color: white, black, and red, with three colors of rice the black, yellow and white (labutan). After preparation, they will arrange the maligay and place everything on it. Once everything is set, the prayer (du'a) will commence. Following the du'a, every person must grab at least one item situated on the maligay.

Thus, the researchers want to study this topic to know the value of this tradition to the residents of the Barangay Bukid Parang-Sulu. The researchers want to share knowledge to the people and to let the new generation know what is importance of tradition in our society. In today's rapidly modernizing world the younger generation focus on advancement has led to a gradual decline in the interest in traditional ritual practices. This study was conducted exclusively in Barangay Bukid, focusing on tangasan, within this specific community. The researchers aim to gain in depth insights to develop a nuanced understanding of traditions, significance and value within the community. The researchers obtained evidence through face-to-face interviews to gather in depth insights, audio recording to capture participants' responses accurately, and documentation for collecting and analyzing relevant.

Tangasan, a distinctive cultural practice specific to Barangay Bukid and is an integral part of its cultural heritage. This uniqueness makes Tangasan a valuable aspect of Barangay Bukid's cultural identity. By studying this tradition, Tangasan, the researchers seek to gain insights to understand the tradition, significance and valued by the community. I appreciate cultural transmission to recognize the importance of passing down cultural traditions through generations. The researchers aim to appreciate the Tangasan by recognizing its uniqueness, understanding the distinct characteristics and cultural significance of tradition. Valuing its importance, identifying the values and meanings associated with the tradition.

Research Problem

The researchers wanted to discover ways to evaluate the importance of traditional culture, Therefore the researcher's aim to answer the following questions:

1. What is tangasan?
2. How tangasan kept the tradition of Barangay Bukid alive?
3. What tangasan makes unique from other traditions?

4. Why tangasan is important to the community of Bukid Parang-Sulu?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This proposed study employed a case study-ethnography research design to examine Tangasan: The Traditional Ritual of Bukid Parang-Sulu. This design is selected to allow the importance of this tradition to the community of Barangay Bukid Parang-Sulu. This study chose to share knowledge and to acknowledge the people, especially the new generations, to let them know about this tradition.

Research Site

The study was conducted in Barangay Bukid, a specific locale where tangasan is practiced, to focus on understanding the tradition within its natural context. The study's locale-based approach can provide valuable insights into the traditions' role in shaping the community's identity and cultural practices.

Participant

The study involved 10 participants, the residents of Barangay Bukid that practiced this tradition, especially the creators, people who have played a role in developing, preserving the tradition, tangasan. The selection of participants likely aimed to gather authentic insights and ensure cultural relevance.

Instruments

Data collection employed a qualitative approach, gathering data through interviews to gathered a depth insights, its history and cultural significance and through observation to study the behaviors and practices associated with the tradition.

Data Gathering Procedures

Data collection conducted after obtaining written consent from the director. The process took place over a period of one week. The researchers ensure that the questionnaires were kept secured and complete throughout the data collection process.

Data Analysis

Using qualitative thematic analysis where responses from interview was coded into the themes. Insights from existing research was used to contextualize the findings ensuring a deeper understanding of the themes and existing knowledge of Tangasan-The Traditional Ritual of Bukid Parang-Sulu.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the data gathered from the participants of this study are coded, analyzed, finalized and categorized into themes. All the personal information shared by

the participants with the researchers will remain confidential and secure. This section also serves as an input that aims to provide knowledge and insights into the significance of their tradition.

Tangasan- the Traditional Ritual of Bukid Parang-Sulu

According to the article of Qiao Wu (2018), The structure of rituals and the epistemological approach to ritual study, rituals function as visualization and activation of the culture facts. Moreover, Rituals and practices in world religions, the religious variables have consistently been found to have a relationship to physical and mental health (Yaden et al 2020).

What is tangasan?

- Tangasan, this is a tradition that every datu as always practiced in the mountains of bukid, in order for us to overcome all the struggles that may arise. This ritual serves as a remedy for us, which is why we continue to observe it. (P1, excerpt 1).

The participants' statement reveals that this culture is maintained by the Barangay Bukid community because it serves as a form of ancestral medicine. Furthermore, Foor (2017) Ancestral Medicine: Rituals for personal and family healing. Simon and Schuster, all cultures possess culturally appropriate health systems. In Southern Africa, traditional healers effectively serve their communities by integrating their practices with patients' traditions and beliefs. This necessitates counselors understand the local context to deliver effective cross-cultural care.

-The tangasan ritual is practiced because of a legend surrounding the child of a datu who feels ill. According to the spiritual leader (mangingitah), the ancestors demanded that the tangasan be performed to restore the child's health. It was believed that this ritual was the only way to lift the curse, and that it was a long-standing desire of their forebears. However, tangasan was not just limited to the datu's family, but also observed by all the residents of bukid. (P2, excerpt 2)

This statement is supported by three additional participants, who explained why this culture is practiced by the community. According to the findings, the culture is preserved because it has become a heritage, and the ritual is believed to be the only way of removing the curse, serving as a healing process for them. However, according to the article, The evolution of ancient healing practices: From shamanism to Hippocratic medicine: A review. Medicine, Ancient healing traditions continue to significantly impact modern healthcare. Cross-cultural exchanges throughout history facilitated the integration of these ancient practices into global healthcare. It advocates for the thoughtful incorporation of herbal remedies and traditional approaches to create a more inclusive and compassionate healthcare system for the future. (Elendu 2024).

Uniqueness of Tangasan to other tradition

- Before the tangasan ritual, preparations are made by creating "maligay", after that they will prepare the 44 kinds of delicacies (bang-bang sug), the 3 colors of chicken the red, white and black, rice with a three colors, including the black, yellow and white (labutan), after that, they will arrange the maligay and put everything on it. (P3, excerpt 3).

Why do we need to make maligay? What is the purpose of this?

- According to the first agreement and the forebears desired, that the spiritual leader (mangingitah) says that maligay in which the only phrase allowed to put everything (foods), making it an essential part of tangasan. (P4, excerpt 4).

- However, food can be placed in the container (bandiha), but as Tausug, we adorn it because we add the “waw” symbol. The “waw” signifies shot “bunuun” its not allowed, instead, maligay is the acceptable way, as agreed upon. (P5, excerpt 4).

The preparation of maligay is a mandatory practice, as it's ensure that the food is handled and presented with utmost respect.

3.3 The significance of Tangasan in the community of Bukid Parang-Sulu

According to Mustanim et al., (2023), Islamic Educational Values in Local wisdom Traditional Tradition of Mappogau Sihanua Karampuang Sinjai District, the most numerous messages of value in the Mappogau Sihanua Karampuang time honored tradition are moral values such as respecting each other, preserving the environment, respecting leaders, cooperation/helping each other, and friendship values.

The benefits of Tangasan in our community are numerous. This tradition has become a way of uniting the relatives who were previously unfamiliar with one another, fostering closeness among them. Additionally, tangasan serves as a reason for distant relatives to reunite every four years. Moreover, this tradition has passed down from our forebears, and we continue to observe it, not only out of respect for our heritage but also out of fear that abandoning it might bring about adverse consequences. Ultimately, Tangasan has become an integral part of our culture identity and serves as a form of spiritual medicine for our community. (C6, except 6).

It serves as a reason for them to reunite as one, while also honoring and preserving their ancestral traditions. Likewise, Quimbo and de la Tore (2024), Ancestral healing rituals and significance of Taky samy in Andean spirituality, the purpose and practices of Taky Samy as important elements of tapestry of ancestral Andean healing rituals. Taky Samy reveals the importance and centrality of the revitalization of indigenous ancestral healing practices to the continuity of Andean spirituality, ontological wisdom and consciousness.

It's held four years because the expenses are not insignificant, and this allow time to save money, by scheduling it every four years, people have enough time to set aside funds so that when the time comes, they are financially prepared. The event is costly because it involves many preparations, such as “maligay” buying chicken, and various dishes. In a way, the four years gap was considered to ensure that organizing tangasan remains manageable and not too burdensome. (P7, excerpt 7).

The community of Barangay Bukid ensures that everyone can participate in the traditional ritual, Tangasan, by holding it for four years, allowing them sufficient time to prepare financially. Therefore, understanding financial management models through the lens of festivals and rituals of rural areas with special reference to south India, financial management is one of the crucial aspects for any organization for growth and development. These financial management systems are not new in Indian context, and these systems are completely indigeneous and unique within the country in every society. (Rahul 2024).

Tangasan bring communities together

Every four the resident (tawuban) of barangay bukid gathered at kasubangan during muharram (month of muslim). They're not permitted to perform individually. All families are needed to make their own maligay before the prayer (du'a) will start. The reason why the resident of bukid bring together it's because of one of the rules of tangasan. At the end of the du'a, it is customary to take a food item from another maligay to ensure the continuation of the tradition. Failing to take at least one food item may result in facing the curse, necessitating the repetition of the ritual. This practice fosters a sense of community and encourages collaboration among participants, ultimately leading to a joyful experience for all. This is the one of the reasons why tangasan being practiced in order for us to unite. (P8, excerpt 8).

According to the article of recapturing the power of ritual to enhance community in aging, rituals return us to the center of who we are. In times of transition, loss, disconnection and loneliness. Moreover, appreciating the rituals of every community is a way to reconnect with the sense of identity, mitigating feelings of loneliness and disconnection. Tradition provides means to understand who we are, as beliefs are integral part of every person in our society. Although we may have differences, appreciating our own culture and respecting others' tradition can foster peace in our society. (Becker and Sangster 2019).

Let's say your parents practice tangasan, if you decide not to follow it when it's your turn would that be, okay?

-No because if you have the bloodline of a datu, you are required to participate in tangasan ritual. This obligation extends to your spouse if they also have the bloodline of a datu. Furthermore, if you have children who get married, they too are expected to perform the tangasan. Failure to do so, especially after getting married, may result in a curse. (P9, excerpt 9).

Practicing the traditional ritual, tangasan, is a kinship and obligation for the residents of bukid. If they can't perform it, they might suffer the curses that their forebears felt. Every generation of their families is expected to perform the ritual, especially when they get married. Additionally, according to Granville (2017), Festive kinship: solidarity, responsibility, and identity formation in Deuteronomy, concludes that the "family" metaphor fosters unity within the Israelite community, encouraging mutual care and support, especially for the vulnerable.

What might happen to you if you do not continue the practices they follow?

- As a result, if you fail not to perform the tangasan, you will suffer the consequences. You will feel the curse (abat) constantly experiencing illness. Consequently, you will incur significant medical expenses, visiting doctors in an attempt to find a cure. If the doctors are unable to help, you will then seek the guidance of mangingitah, only to discover that the root cause of your suffering is your failure to perform the tangasan. (P10, excerpt 10).

According to the findings, it indicates that it is necessary to pass this traditional ritual tangasan down through generations to preserve its fidelity and avoid the curse.

On the other hand, Moku (2024) Promotion of Morality of Traditional Marriage among Abagusi through a Curse (Amasangia), its suggest the importance of teaching future generations about amasangia to uphold marital fidelity and prevent deaths resulting from infidelity.

Therefore, the role of riuals and festivals in preserving Tiwa heritage within the Indian knowledge framework, Tiwa's tradition serve cultural expressions and vesicles for the transmission of traditional knowledge, ensuring that the value, beliefs of customs of Tiwa community are passed out to the future generations (Doloi 2024). Similarly, the Barangay Bukid Parang -Sulu also want to ensure that Tangsan will be known by the future generations.

Conclusions

This traditional ritual, Tangasan, holds significant value for the community of Bukid. Perhaps, every individual needs to practice this tradition to avoid the curses of their forefathers. This study concludes that Tangasan represents the importance of traditional culture in our society. This tradition, where the community of Bukid is the only barangay who do this tradition, holds high value and respect to their forebears.

The history of this tradition has been treasured and passed down through generations so that they know the value of Tangasan. This ritual serves as a tradition in the past years; Their generations value this, even though this is only a tradition.

By studying this tradition, the researchers discovered new lessons. Sharing this knowledge and history, the researchers believe that traditions are actually important in our society. This tradition is of value, and the history behind this has truly been treasured and respected by the younger generations.

Recommendations

The researchers recommend this study to the Local Government Unit (LGU), to promote and preserve the cultural heritage. To inform policies and programs that support cultural identity. To foster community involvement and appreciation of their cultural traditions. By adopting this study's findings, the LGU can develop initiative that showcase and preserve thee Tangasan ritual. To foster community pride and identity through cultural heritage preservation.

The researchers aim to share the findings with the younger generation to ensure the continuation of cultural traditions and values. To educate youth about their community's history and encourage younger generations to value and appreciate cultural heritage. By sharing this knowledge, the researchers hope to empower youth to equip them with a strong sense of cultural identity and pride. Ensure continuity to preserving cultural traditions for future generations.

Deeper understanding, cultural preservation to contribute and appreciate the cultural heritage. Practicing applications, to identify ways to apply lessons from the Tangasan ritual to contemporary society. This research can guide future studies, promoting a deeper understanding and appreciation of traditional ritual and cultural heritage.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study sought ethical approval from the director/principal of Senior High School of Mindanao State University-Sulu, and written consent was obtained. Participants were fully informed about the study's purpose and procedures. Information was selected and handled to maintain confidentiality.

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